

Marhuenda-Fluixà, F, Chisvert-Tarazona, M. J., Palomares-Montero, D., & Tárrega-Mínguez, R. (2022). Guidance in second chance schools: Accompaniment at the core of vocational training. In C. Nägele, N. Kersh, & B. E. Stalder (Eds.), *Trends in vocational education and training research, Vol. V. Proceedings of the European Conference on Educational Research (ECER), Vocational Education and Training Network (VETNET)* (pp. 81–89). <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6976634>

Guidance in Second Chance Schools: Accompaniment at the Core of Vocational Training¹

Marhuenda-Fluixà, Fernando

fernando.marhuenda@uv.es, University of Valencia

Chisvert-Tarazona, María José

maria.jose.chisvert@uv.es, University of Valencia

Palomares-Montero, Davinia

davinia.palomares@uv.es, University of Valencia

Tárrega-Mínguez, Raúl

raul.tarraga@uv.es, University of Valencia

Abstract

Context: Second Chance Schools (E2O, its Spanish acronym) represent an educational response that tries to deal with early school leaving and provide a path for educational re-engagement, labour inclusion and personal reconstruction. This study aims to describe and analyse the guidance model of the Spanish E2O.

Approach: In 2021, we conducted semi-structured interviews with the management of twenty-four schools, 10 professionals in companies hiring youth after finishing their training in E2O, as well as 9 teachers in secondary schools to which former students of E2O returned. Additionally, we conducted a survey among 351 youth who had finished their E2O, and we analysed the record of another 1592 youth who had finished their E2O in schoolyear 2019/2020. We present a descriptive analysis of the quantitative data obtained here.

Findings: The analysis of the interviews shows that the guidance in the E2O is considered a process of personal accompaniment. Some of the defining elements of this process are comprehensiveness (employment, vocational and personal guidance), fluidity in communication through formal and informal channels and the adaptation of the process to each student. The guidance processes begin with an initial phase in which a reception and initial diagnosis process is carried out; it continues with a constant monitoring phase during the itinerary, with formal and informal meetings; and it concludes with a preparation phase for the departure of E2O itself. The quantitative assessment of young people about the orientation processes in the E2O is very positive, although there are some nuances regarding the assessment of flexibility.

Conclusion: The orientation processes developed in the E2Os are a key aspect behind success in educational re-engagement, professional insertion, and personal reconstruction.

Keywords: accompaniment, employment, second chance school, guidance, life project.

¹ This contribution is a short summary, freely translated into English, of an article written in Spanish that is currently under review by a Spanish education journal.

1 Introduction

Our paper focuses on analysing guidance models and processes of training within second chance schools (E2O hereafter, using the Spanish acronym), recalling the notion coined by the European Commission (1995). In Spain, they are basically promoted by non-for-profit organisations also by social economy institutions.

E2O are units that those organisations provide, including transition programs into employment or to reengage in formal education, addressed to young people living in vulnerable circumstances. The Spanish Association of E2O gathers nowadays 43 schools accredited as such through a process of external evaluation. They share educational and social aims, and they are managed by associations, foundations, and cooperatives.

Youth attending these programs usually has a record of early school leaving. Their motives to enrol in E2O vary from the need to overcome suffering, reinforcing emancipation processes, entry into the labour market or the support of relevant others (Christodoulou et al., 2018; Kiprianos & Mpourgos, 2020). One of the main tools E2O use are guidance in different regards, such as personal, vocational, and professional.

Research has described some of the guidance strategies used by E2O, its pace, agents involved as well as its results.

1.1 What is Subject to Counselling, and How is it Conducted?

Villardón-Gallego et al. (2020) have indicated that self-knowledge, an increase in self-confidence, development of a feeling of responsibility and of strategies for emotional coping with conflict are central dimensions of the educational model of E2O. All of these, related to reflection and knowledge of oneself, are precisely the starting point of any guidance process and the basis upon which decision-making and maturity processes are grounded.

Another crucial element is the emotional domain that E2O carry on. Many youths in these schools have the chance to think and plan profound changes in their life trajectories (Martins et al., 2020). This is favoured by well-rooted methodologies in E2O that are also key in guidance, such as group dynamics and activities of the group and individual reflection upon academic aspects (Villardón-Gallego et al., 2020).

Another requirement of guidance is to ‘position students at the core of all decisions’ (McGregor et al., 2015, p. 621), which is also part of the essence of second chances, conscious that their role is not to decide instead of their students, but to equip them with the strategies and opportunities to make their own decisions.

1.2 When to Provide Counselling?

Retention in E2O demands participants to commit to regularly attending the school with a view on the mid and not the short-term. Such a routine of daily attendance, with the accompaniment of the same professionals, provides the youth with the opportunity to face a period of stability that is a change in contrast to their past educational trajectories. More than any program that they attend, the key seems to be in agreeing on personalised itineraries that allow each youth to think and work in their own training process in the mid and long-run (Martínez-Morales, 2021).

Within this framework, pedagogical itineraries in E2O have an average length of two years, varying according to the needs of the youth, entailing training and guidance. There is no rush in E2O, and there is not the pressure of ordinary secondary schools that require an adaptation to the curriculum; rather, on the contrary, it is the school that adapts to the youth to have an impact upon his/her school and life process (Martínez-Clares et al., 2014).

1.3 Who Takes Charge of Counselling?

Research has shown that teachers and trainers worry about the personal and emotional welfare of students (Riele et al., 2017). Professionals in these organisations develop an identity in which emotional dimensions are relevant, such as the ethics of care and welfare of their students, as well as the personalisation of training, to a larger extent than academic performance (Meo & Tarabini, 2020). Teams in E2O provide relevant adults for each youth, supporting them with contrasting views, both in the definition of the itinerary as well as in the evaluation of the achievement of aims.

There is further evidence that when youth is asked for their views, empathy, accompaniment, support, and active listening are valued features (Montserrat & Melendro, 2017). They appreciate key elements that are mobilised by guidance processes with greater intensity than in their experience in previous schools; by establishing a link of trust among youth and educators. E2O, aware of the difficulties of young people in vulnerable circumstances to make decisions, put guidance at the core of their educational model and refer to it rather as an accompaniment than pastoral care, yielding relevance to the personalisation of any intervention (Martins et al., 2020).

1.4 Assessing Guidance in E2O.

Some variables related to guidance processes are daily used in natural as well as planned and purposeful ways in second chance schools. Aspects such as proactivity and the constant work to maintain motivation (Prieto, 2015); flexibility and effort to promote a significative and individualised education (Corchuelo et al., 2016); as well as the construction of a feeling of belonging to a community that provides collective challenges to all its members (González-Faraco et al., 2019).

Espinoza et al. (2020) have identified that the most highly valued dimension by students is the staff in E2O programs, particularly staff with teaching and training responsibilities. This result relates to the appreciation that students show for the capacity of teachers to communicate in the classroom as well as to solve problems. It is also an indicator of the appropriateness of their training itineraries, agreed to thanks to the initial guidance.

Finally, those youth who finalise their itineraries in E2O prove to have a good attitude towards the demands of the workplace, appropriate qualifications regarding the needs of the labour market, as well as engagement, will and interest to work (Villardón-Gallego et al., 2020).

Therefore, our aim in this paper is to analyse personal, vocational, and professional guidance in the model that accredited E2O in Spain conduct nowadays.

2 Method

Our study applies a multimethodological analysis attempting to understand our object study from a holistic perspective. We apply a mixed methodology that combines qualitative and quantitative information and analysis. Our research is conducted in cooperation with the Spanish Association of Second Chance Schools, and it has received the approval of the Ethics in Research Committee of the *Universitat de València*. Qualitative information consisted of interviews with twenty-four E2O management teams, 10 professionals in companies hiring youth after completing their training in E2O and 9 to teachers in secondary schools to which youth returned after E2O. All interviews were conducted between March-May 2021.

Our quantitative study had two sources of information. We conducted a survey of 351 youth who had completed their training in 2019/2020 (out of a total population of 2711 youth as reported by the Spanish Association of Second Chance Schools). In parallel, we had developed a database fulfilled by professionals in E2O, providing data of 1592 individuals out of the

same population, reporting data on their current situation in terms of study or work, as well as the programs they had taken at the E2O. The quantitative analysis we present here is descriptive.

Semi-structured interviews covered issues about curriculum, organisation, counselling, and accreditation. In this paper, we focus on counselling. Information was gathered and analysed with MAXQDA Plus 2020, following the thematic analysis procedure by Braun and Clarke (2006). Therefore, we select relevant issues and proceed to conceptualise them rigorously. We applied the procedure described by Barnes (1996), which consists of successive comparisons among content in the interviews and theoretical concepts as defined in the identification of fundamental themes (Barnes, 1996).

The questionnaire consisted of twenty-three multiple-choice items with a Likert scale. A group of seven experts from three different Spanish universities took part in the process of validation of content, together with four educationalists working in E2O.

The database with data from E2O provides information according to indicators on competencies acquired by youth in relation to their profile and training.

The results of the questionnaire and the database were analysed through descriptive statistics, used to find out the perception of former E2O youth on their curriculum within them.

3 Results

Our analysis of personal, vocational and professional guidance in E2O tries to tackle what is understood by guidance in these schools, what is the role it plays within their educational provision, to what extent counselling becomes part of a wider accompaniment process and how it is conducted, when, who is in charge of it; we also point to the synergies among schools and companies and what is the result of guidance and accompaniment upon the training in E2O.

3.1 What and How is Counselling in E2O

Professional guidance is considered by E2O management as a process of ‘personal accompaniment’ (E28). These organisations make sense of it through several features: integrality, fluent communication, adaptation to each young person and flexibility when it comes to decision-making.

The integral approach is rooted in a typology of guidance (occupational, vocational, and personal) as well as among those who benefit from it, both young persons and their families. E2O provide guidance within a specific subject in the curriculum (FOL, the Spanish acronym for Training and Guidance for Work, *Formación y Orientación Laboral*), both within formal and non-formal vocational education and training: ‘Employment professionals (...) coordinate the preparation of simulated work interviews, which is part of the training process’ (E5). Guidance happens also at the end of the itinerary: ‘What young people do in the classroom (...) where the kids are getting trained while they start preparing their CV, those who want to work’ (E5).

Most E2Os have a wide approach towards guidance, not reduced to labour issues, even in those cases that it is the only expectation of young people. Managers in E2O make it explicit that the axis of guidance processes is vocational guidance, trying to widen the expectations of young people inside and outside the organisation. However, aware of the different needs of youth, schools adapt and agree on viable itineraries.

They also offer guidance at a personal level: ‘We work with young people whose needs are mainly social, personal, crucial in their lives’ (E25). Therefore, E2Os foster accompaniment and guidance from a holistic approach, paying attention not only to vocational and labour issues but also to the social and personal lives of their youth.

Integrality applies to families too that are invited to join guidance processes: ‘Integral means that you work with the mother or father, sometimes even at a psychological level. Perhaps they do not have a job, and therefore we invite them to join some guidance program, and

we try to help them find a job' (E2). Ordinary secondary schools are aware of this kind of support that they are not able to provide, an accompaniment that embeds emotional as well as community dimensions: 'It is basically an accompaniment that includes the emotional side of the person, affections, where the important piece is the person herself (...), it is a real, true significative support ... in all dimensions' (F_E13).

Another relevant feature of guidance in E2O relates to their ability to establish permanent and fluent communication channels, both in training, guidance, and support: 'Yes, we are very insistent in the beginning, then they thank us for being there for them. That they appreciate a different relation (to that of ordinary secondary schools), they tell us so' (E32). Such communication is possible thanks to several channels: 'Group assemblies, individual care, WhatsApp communication, telephone calls, satisfaction questionnaires' (E16).

However, communication would be nothing without the guarantee that students are listened to, and they are able to respond in a way that these organisations are able to satisfy the demands of each of the individuals they serve by 'identifying the needs of each person, as well as their strengths' (E4). Ordinary secondary schools are aware of such individualisation in the guidance process that E2O provide, something that they feel unable to offer and that does not allow them to consider the chance to recover these youth after finishing their process at E2O.

3.2 Guidance Along the Steps of the Itineraries

Another relevant feature of guidance in E2O refers to the use of time as a key to allowing them to progress at the pace of each youth. Decisions are taken with enough time, and they are subject to review. Guidance is defined in these institutions as '(...) the way in which one starts taking a position in his/her own life, and then the moment will come when you decide which direction you want to take' (E24). Guidance is therefore structured all along the process, and so it is identified across different moments: welcome, follow-up, preparation to leave the E2O and follow-up once you have left the E2O.

Upon the arrival of the young person to the school, the welcoming process is key to success. In this initial moment, the young person must find his/her place within the school while jointly defining his/her aims and planning a personalised itinerary. A vocational project is designed to consider expectations, interests, personal trajectory, and profile. Despite the relevance of this initial process, the resulting itinerary and agreed decisions are reviewed along the whole process within the E2O.

Some schools apply a diagnostic of employability in the welcoming phase, which may lead to an itinerary where training plays a minor role while guidance and entry into the labour market become most relevant: 'A diagnostic of employability that is performed slowly and that identifies particular needs of the young person, either about training, guidance or access into the labour market' (E27).

The follow-up phase is 'constant' (E8), and it allows to assess whether 'the aims of the itinerary are achieved' (E27). This phase evaluates the progress and allows to review decisions. It is performed through 'the lens of personal accompaniment' (E28), hence safeguarding proximity and being close to the young person. If changes are necessary, these are not circumscribed only to the individual but also to the school, that must rethink its relation to the young person through a new turn in the training itinerary: 'Plans, above all, must be planned but also reviewed and redirected' (E9).

Once the itinerary has finished, guidance is directed towards the preparation of exit of the individual, often towards employment, upon agreement of the young person and the team: 'Towards the end of the school year, we work a lot upon labour dimensions, job interview and all the abilities the youth have developed' (E25). Even though guidance refers mainly to continuing training out of the E2O: 'guidance towards qualifying in different types of studies' (E42).

Once the itinerary is over in the institution, there is a follow-up of at least six months, which is mandatory in E2O to achieve accreditation. This follow-up may be face to face or by telephone: ‘Once over (...) we have six months to reinforce and conduct a follow-up, while the relation to the youth becomes looser, both face to face and by phone’ (E27).

The young person ‘sees how the process goes by, considering the entry-level and trusting in the support achieved towards a better future’ (E17). This process from the welcoming stage to the final one cannot work if young people do not have a proactive attitude towards accompaniment and guidance: ‘There is a common requirement in our school: either you have the motivation, or this will not work out well’ (E4).

3.3 Who Conducts Counselling in E2O: Specialisation and Allocation of Responsibilities?

Agents involved in guidance have a background which is mainly psychological, despite some teams are multidisciplinary, incorporating complementary experience or even vocation: ‘We have social workers, psychologists, pedagogues, local development agents ..., so in the end, it is not so much which is your background, but which is your experience or even which is your calling’ (E34). However, E2Os insist on training and specialisation of staff in charge of guidance: ‘Master programs linked to guidance or counselling ...’ (E17).

In some cases, an area has been developed within the organisation behind E2O in which staff oversees prospecting and mediation actions: ‘They spend all day out in the street, establishing relations to companies for the sake of the people we work for’ (E8). They try to consolidate their work experience modules and the chances of hiring people. Similarly, companies make explicit the meaning achieved through the agreements they sign with E2O: ‘These are commitments which are not mandatory though we generally apply them so that we get people for performing a stage of work experience and we may hire someone too, perhaps one to three new staff in a year or two’ (T_E26).

There are initiatives where E2O take the lead to guarantee the appropriateness of the experience for the youth they serve, like projects that sometimes require training in the school and in the company: ‘Other projects that we have (...) are mixed training with companies where we provide some training, the company provides some, facilitates work experience ...’ (E35).

These are synergies that some E2Os are still trying to develop by establishing good relations with companies. They get in touch with SMEs that are close to them: ‘We have tried to respond to such demands by connecting to small companies, looking in detail in our own area, but we still have a lot to improve here’ (E13). There are cases in which there is a clear lack of proper staff as well as funding to add this service within the schools: ‘We need much time to establish good relations to companies, we do not have the time for that, we do not get the funding for that’ (E13).

3.4 Assessing Guidance: Provisional Analysis of the Results

Guidance is considered very relevant by these schools: ‘It is guidance and accompaniment (...) where our success relies upon’ (E34). In fact, it is a service used by all youth who attend E2O.

Former E2O students are very satisfied with guidance. They get average evaluations around 3,56 (out of 4) in dimensions like ‘I have received guidance to take decisions’ or 3.29 in ‘I have been able to know and select among different training chances’. Another relevant dimension is that of ‘I have started a training and, if I thought I made a mistake, I could change to another one ...’, with an average of 2.75, perhaps because the training offer in E2O is not as varied as it might be.

When analysing the importance awarded to training and guidance, we observe that occupational guidance is extremely valued, with 89 % of students agreeing to it and an average of

3.46. However, it is somewhat below the relevance achieved by obtaining the GCSE and slightly above vocational training. Low behind those falls the weight of the preparation of the entrance examinations to formal VET.

Results of E2O six months after finalising the itineraries show that 49 % of young people keep studying, while 30 % neither study nor work. Nevertheless, this percentage decreases to 24 % 9 months after leaving the E2O. Given that young people search for a job, the lack of it, according to the economic context, has a strong impact upon vulnerable youth. We need to examine longer periods of time to capture the effect of E2O on labour itineraries of youth, and, in some cases, there is a need to widen the provision and intensity of guidance services beyond the training period in E2O.

4 Discussion and Conclusions

Guidance in E2O is part of a wider process, that of personalised accompaniment, which constitutes the axis of socio-educational intervention in these schools. Guidance is not a momentary action, but it is rather incorporated into the educational process that is shaped around the personalised itinerary. We agree with Ceniceros (2003) in considering the itinerary both as the result of guidance and as a tool to develop guidance itself. The authorship of the itinerary lies in the hands of the young person, and it is the mission of the staff to provide guidance in order to help the young person a) clarify his/her needs; b) get a diagnosis through which to improve his/her abilities and employability; c) help the young person to raise consciousness about his/her potential, limits, circumstances and the context surrounding him/her; all of these both in labour as well as in civic terms. In accordance with Martins et al. (2020), we consider E2O as an opportunity to reflect and plan profound changes in occupational and life trajectories.

The itinerary revised over time allows the youth to explore his/her capacities, interests, and expectations, but also to test them in different training programs through the performance of practical activities that allow him/her to make mistakes and correct him/herself. Exploration is an exercise prior to engagement, and both are more accessible before the lack of pressure of time. However, the itinerary itself requires each youth the commitment to exploration and, later, to select based on experience and the knowledge of different occupational possibilities, as Villardón-Gallego et al. (2020) have pointed out.

These decisions are taken upon the basis of formative assessment, which is, in turn, possible thanks to the lack of curriculum mandates behind most of the training programs offered by E2O, taking advantage of not being formal VET. Assessment is at the service of guidance, which provides relevant information about each youth.

Furthermore, guidance is supported upon different dimensions of the life of the youth, as Jacinto (2017) has shown, while E2Os set the material conditions that make possible, sufficient life circumstances to make guidance useful and relevant. Networks in which E2O take part are a fundamental resource for this.

Guidance is, therefore, at the service of shaping a life project that, at the same time, becomes crucial for the process of personal re-structuration of the young person, an internal process through which the young person matures, a task intrinsic to adolescence and relevant for transitions into adulthood.

Even work experience in companies, the same as occupational qualification, has an instrumental role beyond qualification. The conditions provided for the young person to develop his/her itinerary allow him/her to taste, make mistakes and to better define a life project. The length of the itineraries is also personalised, the same as the access to training, which is permanently open along the schoolyear. Time runs in favour and not against the interest of the young person, as Zacarés and Linares had explained (2006).

Education addressed to young people with school trajectories that lack structure and which aim to improve success needs guidance to occupy a central position in educational practice, as is the case in E2O, without renouncing specialisation but involving all the staff members.

E2Os have ambitious aims with their students, aims that go far beyond the merely academic and professional domains. Along their itineraries, processes of personal reflection are fostered that help young people analyse the motives that caused their difficulties along their attendance to ordinary schools, and these allow them to make decisions about the direction they want to take for their lives in the short, medium, and long term, not only regarding their academic or occupational aspirations but also about their personal lives.

References

- Barnes, D.M. (1996). An analysis of the Grounded theory method and the concept of culture. *Qualitative Health Research*, 6(3), 429-441. <https://doi.org/10.1177/104973239600600309>
- Braun, V., & Clarke, V. (2006). Using thematic analysis in psychology. *Qualitative Research in Psychology*, 3(2), 77-101. <https://doi.org/10.1191/1478088706qp063oa>
- Ceniceros, J.C. (2003). *Orientación sociolaboral basada en itinerarios. Una propuesta metodológica para la intervención con personas en riesgo de exclusión*. Fundación Tomillo.
- Christodoulou, M., Kiprianos, P., & Papachristopoulou, E. (2018). Becoming a Lifelong Learner through Life Disruptions: Exploring Motivational Pathways in Second Chance Schools' Students. *Sociological Research Online*, 23(3), 606-621. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1360780418770460>
- European Commission (1995). *Libro Blanco Sobre la Educación y la Formación. Enseñar y Aprender. Hacia la Sociedad del Conocimiento*. <https://evalua.catedu.es/documentos/aragon/NormativaVarios/>
- Corchuelo, C., Cejudo, C.M., González, J. C., & Morón, J.A. (2016). Al borde del precipicio: las escuelas de segunda oportunidad, promotoras de inserción social y educativa. *International Journal of Educational Research and Innovation*, 6, 95-109. <https://upo.es/revistas/index.php/IJERI/article/view/1848>
- Espinoza, O., González, L., McGinn, N., & Castillo, D. (2020). Alternative education programs for high school age students in Chile. *Education and Urban Society*, 52(4), 561-589. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0013124519879428>
- González-Faraco, J.C., Luzón-Trujillo, A., & Corchuelo-Fernández, C. (2019). Initial vocational education and training in a second chance school in Andalusia (Spain): A case study. *The Australian Educational Researcher*, 46(5), 827-842. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13384-019-00304-8>
- Jacinto, C. (2017). Redistribución y afectividad como dimensiones de la justicia social. Las intervenciones del tercer sector en las transiciones de la educación al trabajo. *Profesorado, Revista de Currículum y Formación de Profesorado*, 21(4), 177-195. <https://doi.org/10.30827/profesorado.v21i4.10051>
- Kiprianos, P., & Mpourgos, I. (2020). Back to school: From dropout to Second Chance Schools. *Journal of Adult and Continuing Education*, 28(1), 27-48. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1477971420979725>
- Martínez-Clares, P., Pérez-Cusó, F.J., & Martínez-Juárez, M. (2014). Orientación profesional en educación secundaria. *Revista Electrónica Interuniversitaria de Formación del Profesorado*, 17(1), 57-71. <http://dx.doi.org/10.6018/reifop.17.1.198841>
- Martínez-Morales, I. (Coord.) (2021). *La formación en las escuelas de segunda oportunidad (E2O) acreditadas en España: perfil, trayectoria y condiciones de éxito de las y los jóvenes*. Ministerio de Educación y Formación Profesional.
- Martins, F., Carneiro, A., Campos, L., Ribeiro, L.M., Negrão, M., Baptista, M.I., & Matos, R. (2020). Derecho a una segunda oportunidad: lecciones aprendidas de la experiencia de quien abandonó y regresó a la educación. *Pedagogía Social: Revista Interuniversitaria*, 36, 139-153. <http://orcid.org/0000-0002-8853-786X>
- McGregor, G., Mills, M., Te Riele, K., & Hayes, D. (2015). Excluded from school: Getting a second chance at a 'meaningful' education. *International Journal of Inclusive Education*, 19(6), 608-625. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13603116.2014.961684>
- Meo, A., & Tarabini, A. (2020). Teachers' identities in second chance schools: A comparative analysis of Buenos Aires and Barcelona. *Teaching and Teacher Education*, 88, 102963. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tate.2019.102963>
- Montserrat, C., & Melendro, M. (2017). ¿Qué habilidades y competencias se valoran de los profesionales que trabajan con adolescencia en riesgo de exclusión social? Análisis desde la acción socioeducativa. *Educación XXI*, 20(2), 113-135. <https://doi.org/10.5944/educxx1.19034>
- Prieto, B. (2015). El camino desde la vulnerabilidad escolar hacia el desenganche educativo. El papel de las escuelas de segunda oportunidad en la estrategia contra el abandono educativo. *Profesorado. Revista de Currículum y Formación de Profesorado*, 19(3), 110-125. <https://recyt.fecyt.es/index.php/profesorado/article/view/43633>

- Riele, K., Mills, M., McGregor, G., & Baroutsis, A. (2017). Exploring the affective dimension of teachers' work in alternative school settings. *Teaching Education*, 28(1), 56-71. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10476210.2016.1238064>
- Villardón-Gallego, L., Flores-Moncada, L., Yáñez-Marquina, L., & García-Montero, R. (2020). Best Practices in the Development of Transversal Competences among Youths in Vulnerable Situations. *Education Sciences*, 10(9), 230. <https://doi.org/10.3390/educsci10090230>
- Zacarés, J.J., & Llinares, L. (2006). Experiencias positivas, identidad personal y significado del trabajo como elementos de optimización del desarrollo de los jóvenes. Lecciones aprendidas para los futuros programas de cualificación profesional inicial. *Revista de Educación*, 341, 123-147.

Biographical notes

Dr **Fernando Marhuenda-Fluixá** is a full university professor at the University of Valencia. He teaches didactics and organisation of VET and social education, as well as on the social economy and coordinates the research group *Transicions*.

Dr **María José Chisvert-Tarazona** is a professor at the Department of Didactics and School Organisation, University of Valencia. She conducts research on Educational Management, Adult Education and Didactics as a member of the research group *Transicions*.

Dr **Davinia Palomares-Montero** is a professor at the Department of Didactics and School Organisation, University of Valencia. She conducts research on social entrepreneurship and second chance schools as a member of the research group *Transicions*.

Dr **Raúl Tárraga-Mínguez** is a professor at the Department of Didactics and School Organisation, University of Valencia. He was previously a special education teacher. His research interests are inclusive education and teacher education.